

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF DRAMATURGY IN LITERATURE

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Abstract. *Dramaturgy always addresses a person, seeks to reveal the secrets of his heart, tries to understand the essence of human relations, no matter whether this person is historical or modern. In the future, it is necessary to create an opportunity for our young artists to swing their pencils skillfully. The creation of workshops in the centers of each district, the constant activity of circles of young pencil artists in music schools, houses of culture, this, of course, inspires every artist, encourages him to work, and one day he will inevitably create masterpieces.*

Key words: *Composition, prologue, exposition, development of events, conflict, Knot, climax, denouement, epilogue, fable, drinking, plot.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДРАМАТУРГИИ В ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

Аннотация. *Драматургия всегда обращается к человеку, стремится раскрыть тайны его сердца, пытается понять суть человеческих отношений, независимо от того, является ли этот человек историческим или современным. В будущем необходимо создать возможность для наших молодых художников умело размахивать карандашами. Создание мастерских в центрах каждого района, постоянная деятельность кружков юных художников-карандашников в музыкальных школах, домах культуры - это, конечно, вдохновляет каждого художника, побуждает его к труду, и однажды он неизбежно создаст шедевры.*

Ключевые слова: *композиция, пролог, экспозиция, развитие событий, конфликт, узел, кульминация, развязка, эпилог, басня, пьянка, сюжет.*

It has been a century since the dramatic genre entered Uzbek literature. Behbudi's "Padarkush", recognized as the first dramatic work, was written in 1911. This Uzbek dramaturgy, which has a hundred years of history and experience, has always developed more slowly than other literary genres, except for the beginning of the last century and the period of the Second World War. This decline is especially noticeable in the 70s and 80s, which was called the "recession period" of the last century, and the first years of independence. There are certain objective and subjective reasons for such laziness. First of all, it should be noted with regret that there are very few special creators in our literature who are engaged only in dramaturgy. Some of them do not become famous and become permanent partners of theaters by creating stage works of the discovery level. Secondly, even if such a talented drama is created and staged, there is a problem of attracting the audience to it. Thirdly, due to the market economy, the playwright is not getting rich with his work. Despite this, in the last 20 years, the drama has not been created, the stage has not been empty, and more or less the audience has entered the theater.

Most importantly, in recent years, dramaturgy has been renewed in terms of form and content, and the possibilities of the genre have expanded. Artists began to make good use of the living experiences of world dramaturgy. According to tradition, many poetic dramas were born in these years. "Tragedy of Istanbul" by E. Vahidov, by A. Oripov Works such as "Sahibqiron", "The Secretary of Rasulullah" by U. Kochkar, "Yusuf and Zulayho" by R. Bobojan were written in this way. The development and renewal of dramaturgy is evident in the expansion of the scope of the

subject. In this regard, it should be noted that there has been an increase in stage works, especially on historical themes.

To history due to the change of attitude, appreciation of the artistic, scientific and spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, study of historical sources, our nation experienced the process of self-realization. In particular, stage plays in various genres were created about complex historical figures such as Amir Temur, Ahmad al-Fargani, and Mashrab. Among them, the historical drama "Fatihi Muzaffar yakhud bir parivash kissasi" by the people's writer of Uzbekistan Odil Yaqubov takes an important place. It is worth noting that O. Yaqubov is an experienced writer in dramaturgy. That's it experience and skill gave good results in the last drama of the artist. During this period, many dramas on modern themes were born. In this regard, Erkin Khushvaqtoy, Salahiddin Sirojiddinov, Usman Azim, Sanjarali Imamov, Khaliq Khursandov, Nasrullo Qabil, Komil Avaz Toir Yunusov have worked effectively.

The works of some of them became the permanent repertoire of theaters and satisfied the audience's thirst and increased their interest in theaters. Because it has long been known that the theater is the most effective and lively means of educating the people in the spirit of spiritual enlightenment. The scene is a mirror of real life. In this sense, among the above-mentioned playwrights, E. Khushvaktov took home the prize. He referred more to the materials of folklore, folklore-ethnographic topics and traditions that are dying in our national traditions. E. Khushvaktov's "Chimildiq", staged one after another at the National Theater of Uzbekistan.

As much as possible, he tries to absorb the spirit and essence of the Uzbek people's traditional traditions, enrich them with new traditions, and improve the attitude of the young generation in his songs such as "Kalliq Oyin", "Qizil olma", "Andishali Kelinchak". in some places it is achieved. Chosen to express his intention

does not achieve success in methods and forms. For example, the dramas "Chimildiq" and "Qalliq Oyin" are primarily based on light-hearted events, the relationships between the characters are extremely artificial, instead of raising the value of our traditions arouses hatred. In these dramas, the resolution does not satisfy the audience. Each artist chooses a specific subject. Like a fetus, it develops inside him, in his mind.

From the topic chosen by the author for the upcoming work then the next problem in front of him will be transverse. This problem consists in determining the structure of the work. Of course, the construction of the work, i.e. defining its content, is also considered very responsible. Here is the composition of the author's work falls into action. In fact, the word composition is derived from the Latin language, and in Uzbek it means structure, construction. The composition of the work is related not only to the system of events, but also to the construction of words and their presentation. Because "in works of art, only images, language and stylistic tools are the author serves a specific idea that is being promoted. The structure of the work, like the above, is absorbed into the author's idea. If the images and image tools are not placed in a certain order, both the parts of the image will lose their balance and harmony. No matter how skilled the artist is, his idea and is not considered to have fully achieved its goal. Therefore, if the creator's goal, idea, point of view is not consistent and clear, his work will not be thorough and successful in terms of structure. If every detail, every element in the work requires each other, if they are absorbed into each other, this is called harmony.

Dramaturgy always appeals to a person, tries to reveal the secrets of his soul, tries to understand the essence of human relations, it does not matter if this person is historical or modern. In the future, it is necessary to create an opportunity for our young artists to skillfully swing their pencils. Creation of workshops in the centers of every district, the constant activity of young pencil writers' circles in music schools, cultural centers, this certainly inspires every artist, encourages them to work, and one day it is inevitable that they will produce masterpieces.

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